

Embodiment, performance and shared transformation:- A quest to understand the idea of 'Folklore' in Bangladesh

By
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'Folklore' as an invalid category in Bangladesh

Bangladesh has diverse and different versions and narratives of 'folklore'. If we, however, would like to engage with and make any attempt to the understanding of the genres and multiplicity, we have to address the problems of the very definition of 'folklore' in our modern living, in the disciplinary domain and in the discourses of protecting and preserving them. The category of 'folklore' including various and often, conflicting enactments of oral narratives, myths, legends, stories, riddles, performances, rhymes, etc. has emerged within the unequal encounter between the 'west' and 'the rest'. The projects of modernity under the colonial and nationalistic paradigms have transformed, incorporated, rejected and consequently essentialised the notions and studies of 'folklore' and the very desire and sensibilities to protect and preserve them.

In the post-Enlightenment Europe, a growing interest in the popular culture including the genres of narratives defined as folklore was concomitant with and conditioned

by the rise of the nation-state and nationalism. Various structures and versions of narrative making attracted attentions from the upper-class intellectuals for various reasons. The fundamental among them was the encounter with the non-western people, cultures and religions. Many scholars have already pointed to the differential, yet far-reaching consequences of these encounters. The societies, lives, customs, rituals, performative narratives, myths and all other aspects of non-European life was the object of ethnographic inquiry and knowledge production during this colonial and imperial expansion. Many modern academic and institutional disciplines, including anthropology, sociology and folklore studies, formed and evolved during this period.

The folklore thus, on the one hand, became representative of the people who possessed a tradition of oral history and performative narratives. It was constructed and selected as one of the standards to determine who are civilized and who are not. The oral traditions, in contrast to the written traditions of civilizations, on the scale of socio-cultural evolutionary framework, were yard-

sticks to construct and represent the non-western societies, cultures and religions within a distinct and inferior stage of evolution which was long gone for European (or western selfhood). Yet, to understand the (pre) history of European self it was also necessary- as the post-enlightenment intellectuals, administrators, travelers and missionaries claimed, to study the non-European oral and performative traditions. In this way, we have to acknowledge that initially folklore studies were essentially entwined with the construction and representation of 'the other' in relation to the 'European self'. This was true even in a slightly later period when they were identified by the orientalist as romanticised and glorified essence of non-Western 'other'. When the structures of these narratives- with their unique, open-ended and infinite varieties were being studied, textualised, analysed and represented, they were reified and homogenised according to the conditions and standards of Colonial Modernity. In South Asia many of these standards were fundamentally Victorian with their particular moral, religious, elitist and dominating predicaments. In this process, the narrative structures those were

compatible to these versions under the projects of colonial modernity, gained their ascendancy. They were refashioned, reshaped, translated and represented in different manners, they were meticulously surveyed, documented and museolised, and transformed into a referent to the lost glories, hidden symbols, deep structures, and to the functional role they played for maintaining and transforming the equilibrium of the 'people without (written) history'.

Embodied, performative and shared traditions in subaltern domain

In South Asia, the native folklorists were deeply influenced by the conceptual and methodological paradigms. They attempted to represent their enterprises of collecting, documenting, translating and archiving in the name of protecting and preserving the folklores as fossil remains from the janaparisar (popular domains). The nationalist and regionalist turn in folklore studies in the name of protecting and preserving the traditions inherited the same conceptual and methodological apparatus from their colonial masters. Many of the religious traditions were essentialised, sacralised and sanitised. Thus, in Bengal, we can see the terms like 'Obscure religious cults' for the alternative religious traditions which fought against the tyranny of dominant religious worldviews and modernity. The traditions of *adivasis* were textualised, classified and published with the ethnographic details which enabled the dominant class, caste, religious and ethnic groups to construct a network of surveillance and management of the people at the margins.

The traditions, which are now famous as belonging to *dehotattwo* (various distinct traditions of/about body), were homogenised and reduced into narratives of hedonism, promiscuity and perversion by the nineteenth century scholars. The scholars, who claimed to protect them, basically, stripped them of the body and

Shared reading from Manasa angala by the women in Guptabari of Barisal (Photo: Shuvo Sen)

the performances or in contrast, connected them to the liberating humanism by refashioning them according to the Victorian notion of body, love, devotion and sexuality. For example, when in Bangladesh Fakir Lalon Sai or the other gurus are celebrated as representing the resistance against the dominant and authoritative religious and casteist practices, they are disassociated from the multiple histories of traditions of Tantrism, Sufism and Vaisnavism. They are transformed into icons of religious harmony and secular humanism. Their embodied performative rituals and worldviews are either represented as essentially body centric in terms of the Victorian notion of sexuality, or as a practice of sexual emancipation in modern and liberal humanist sense. Although they seem to be contradictory to each other, like many other essential contradictions of modernism at large, this particular example of appropriating different traditions in the contemporary popular culture can be cited as only one of the numerous ways in which 'folklore' is defined, referred to and appropriated into the mainstream authoritative discourses of elitist nationalism. It is evident from the works of many contemporary social scientists that complex processes and structures of appropriation, refashioning and rejection are at interplay in the actions of Nationalism.

Another important aspect pointed at by Kamaluddin Kabir, a faculty of Department of Theatre of Jagannath University, could be touched upon¹. Referring to the problems of appropriation and translation, he referred to the term '*geetika*' in the celebrated and monumental collection of different varieties of narratives of songs and performances under the title of '*Maimansigh Gitika*' which were primarily collected by Acharya Dinesh Chandra Sen. Kabir referred to the misleading use of the term '*Geetika*' which is a direct translation of ballad from the western context. Originally, these are popularly identified as '*geetaranga*' (songs with embodied performances), according to Kabir, in that regional context. The entire seminal project of collection and textualisation, albeit noteworthy on its own accord, splits the body and its enactment in performative context in connection to the audience. Similar pattern of disjunction of body from the tradition in particular and selective imposition of body on specific traditions [i.e. various genres of *keertan* performed in different parts of Bangladesh- e.g.- *Paalagaan, Jaarigaan, Saarigaan, Bhaitiyali, Bhawaiya, Gajirgaan*, street performances of popular songs specially during the auspicious

¹ Kamaluddin Kabir- Personal Communication.

occasions of the birth or death anniversary of a *sufi* or *fakir* or saint, *royani* (the embodied enactment from *Manasha Mangal* in Barisal of Southern part of Bangladesh), etc.] can be mentioned in this regard. Interestingly, the works on popular culture in contemporary Bangladesh have also raised the particular issue of selection, appropriation and reshaping of particular binary categories as 'folklore' and 'mainstream'.

The '*Baul-Fakir*' traditions and songs, exhibited as a homogenised category of 'folk-songs' or folk-culture, are well celebrated and represented as the emblem of nationality and identity by the elite upper and middle class in Bengal region. The entire articulation and power relations in this representation processes are also extremely problematic. The contemporary consumerism and politics of representation have selectively manipulated various genres of traditions and their representations in popular domain under the rubric of '*Baul/Fakir song*', culture, and lifestyle. They are one of the most celebrated products in commoditised consumer culture these days. The invention of the categories in Bangladesh, like *lokgaan* (folk songs), *loksahitya* (folk literature), *loksanskriti* (folk culture), *loknritya* (folk dance), *loknatya* (folk drama), etc., overtly represent homogenisation and reductionism of differences, plurality, and embodiment into authorised, sanctioned and commoditised categories of 'folk'. It is, therefore, important to attend to the ways in which sensibilities, dispositions and practices are entangled to the differential perceptions and also the manifestations of body in traditions which go through complex processes of reconfigurations and rejections. It is crucial, under these circumstances, to delve into the questions about how and why these processes are articulated within complex structures of power and capital.

The image of a *Baul* singer in

Performance during the festival celebrating Peer Sultan Mahisawar's birthday at Mahasthan, Bogra (photo: Masud Karim)

Royani, a performative enactment of Manasamangala at Kaunia, Barisal (Photo: Ashok Ghosh)

Rituals of Buri worship on an archaeological site during excavation at Birol (Photo: Swadhin Sen)

mainstream media and narrative is a stereotype developed out of romantic nostalgia about the 'cultural roots' on one side and of reshaping them according to the dominant taste, expression and capital, on the other. It is interesting to note, in reference to Manosh Chowdhury, a faculty in Department of Anthropology of Jahangirnagar University and

a researcher on Popular Culture, that the very category of 'Folk' is very important to negotiate with contemporary Bangladesh². He argues that the traditions that are part and parcel of the subaltern domain are embodied, performative, oral, open-ended, flexible, and transformative. In the fluid space of intimate relationship among the performers,

2 Manosh Chowdhury, Sonabandhur Pereteo Bhalobasar Sushil Discourse. In S. M. Nurul Alam, Aion Naher and Manosh Chowdhury (eds.) *Sampratit Nribigyan*, Department of Anthropology, Jahangirnagar University, 1999

the plural audience, and discursive traditions themselves the ownership to these traditions develops and evolves. There are no copyright or singular ownership on the materials that are being enacted. They transform according to the regions, audience and discursivity.

This is what we may call the art of storytelling and performing in corporeal intimacy. The tangible and the intangible are inseparable in contrast to the transnational and official heritage vocabularies. These obvious, yet (un)comfortable terrain of jan (public/popular) are subverted completely when they are represented in a selective way as traditional or as tangible heritage within the category of 'folk' by the educated Bengali/Bangladeshi middle class and/or by the nationalist discourse in a symbiotic relationship with the transnational definition of heritage.

The essentiality of the recognition of plurality and flexibility of traditions

'Heritage' is an idea, a process and a representation, though it is assumed and presented as something taken-for-granted. Scholars like Laurajane Smith³ have attracted our attention to these processual and representational aspects of 'heritage'. When we say something as our heritage, we are giving particular meaning to that something; the meanings are generated within a certain process and structures. The disjuncture between tangible and intangible is an imposed one. In the popular domain, performative and embodied oral traditions are entangled to the archaeological or material domain. For example, the site that is being excavated by our team right now is identified and recognised by the local Hindu communities as the place of a local goddess named Buri. There is also a place/than of

Epiphany and performative rituals at Madhabgaon Buruj Mound, an archaeological site considered by the locals as the place of local deities, at Kaharol, Diranjpur (Photo: Didar Hossein)

a peer (Muslim religious saint). Elaborate performances and rituals are organised on this particular site. At the same time, by excavating the site on which a Brahmanical Temple of c. 10th – 11th century CE has been identified, we, as archaeologists, are generating new and additional meanings. Given that the entire excavation works are also performative, the oral history, the rituals and performances and our performances- act in conjunction to generate new meanings in both official and popular domains. At the same time, alternative and multiple narratives of the invoked traditions are being produced and reproduced throughout our work on the site.

The idea of tradition and the idea of heritage are connected, yet they are different. Traditions are open ended, flexible, selected to be represented as something immemorial, unchangeable and given. Heritage, on the other hand, is processual and manufactured according to the authoritative discourses. The arguments by Ashis Nandy on the difference between Myth and History and the interpretation of oral traditions by several historians of subaltern studies could be referred

to as examples to point at the ways in which alternative narratives could be created for a more nuanced and multilayered understanding of traditions. Elsewhere, I have also attempted to attend to these traditions from the perspectives of Public Archaeology⁴.

In Bangladesh, the oral and embodied performative traditions and their reconfigurations must be taken into account for any initiative to protect and preserve them. Their character as fluid, transformative and shared on differential discourses of embodiments have to be delved into and negotiated, first, by recognising all these characteristics, second, by engaging with the historicity of the category of folklore, and third, by asserting the fact that communities are the owners of these shared traditions. There is nothing 'pure' or 'original' category of 'folklore'. By abandoning the idea and characters of the category of 'folklore', by embracing the heterogeneous, non-definitive and performative dimensions of traditions, which are continuously being born, shifting and reconfigured, we may usefully start thinking about inhabiting these traditions in a more meaningful way.

3 Laurajane Smith, *Discourses of heritage: Implications for archaeological community practice*. Nuevo MundoMundosNuevos, 2012 (<http://nuevomundo.revues.org/64148>).

4 Ashis Nandy, *History's Forgotten Doubles* (<http://jan.ucc.nau.edu/~sj6/nandy%20history%27s%20forgotten%20doubles.pdf>) Shahid Amin, *Gandhi as Mahatma: Gorakhpur District, Eastern UP, 1921-2* (<http://jan.ucc.nau.edu/sj6/AminGandhiasMahatma.pdf>). Swadhin Sen, *Our past, their past(s): Cultural Heritage and Popular domain in Bangladesh* (<http://old-archives.newagebd.net/special.php?spid=7&id=26>)